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Flipped Classroom vs. Conventional Classroom

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Abstract:

As we know the teaching is process of nurture out the inherited potential of the students by the teachers to use their science of knowledge and arts of teaching and portrait the vibrant colours of thoughts on the cognition of students. There is no teaching approach is perfect in itself all have some pros and cons simultaneously but the best result of students achievement of based on the wisely decision taken by teachers and adopt different teaching approaches based on the content, nature and discipline of the subject. There are two different approaches to teaching and learning (1) Flipped Classroom Approach and (2) Traditional Classroom Approach. Both these approaches are contradictory to each other but it can be used as complementary to enhance the teaching learning process by teachers. In this article author discussed the comparison between Flipped Classroom vs. Conventional Classroom in their context of their key features, advantage and disadvantage.

Keywords: *Flipped Classroom, Traditional Classroom and Teaching Learning Process.*

Introduction

The flipped classroom and the traditional classroom are two different approaches to teaching and learning. The flipped classroom reverses the traditional learning environment by delivering instructional content outside of the classroom and engaging students in learning activities during class time. The traditional classroom, on the other hand, is a more teacher-centered approach, where the teacher delivers instruction to the entire class at once.

Flipped classroom

A flipped classroom is an instructional strategy and a type of blended learning, which aims to increase student engagement and learning by having pupils complete readings at home and work on live problem-solving during class time. This pedagogical style moves activities, including those that may have traditionally been considered homework, into the classroom.

The flipped classroom is a pedagogical approach that reverses the traditional learning environment by delivering instructional content outside of the classroom and engaging students in learning activities during class time. This approach is often used in conjunction with technology, such as video lectures, online readings, and interactive exercises.

In a flipped classroom, students typically watch video lectures or read online materials at home before coming to class. This allows them to learn the new material at their own pace and on their own time. During class time, students then work on activities that allow them to apply what they have learned, such as problem-solving exercises, group projects, or hands-on experiments.

Benefits of a flipped classroom

- **Increased student engagement:** Students are more likely to be engaged in the learning process when they are actively involved in activities, rather than passively listening to lectures.
- **Improved student learning:** Flipped classrooms have been shown to improve student learning outcomes in a variety of subjects.
- **Increased flexibility for students:** Students can learn at their own pace and on their own time outside of class.
- **More personalized instruction:** Teachers can provide more personalized instruction to students during class time, since they are not spending time lecturing.

Challenges of the flipped classroom

While there are many potential benefits to using a flipped classroom approach, there are also some challenges that teachers and students may face. These challenges include:

- **Ensuring that students have access to the necessary technology:** Not all students have access to a computer and the internet at home. This can be a barrier to using a flipped classroom approach.

- **Providing support for students who struggle with learning**
- **independently:** Some students may need extra support when learning independently outside of class. Teachers can provide support by offering office hours, creating online discussion forums, or providing students with the contact information of a tutor.
- **Managing class time:** It can be challenging to manage class time effectively in a flipped classroom. Teachers need to be careful not to spend too much time lecturing, and they need to make sure that all students have an opportunity to participate in learning activities.

Tips for flipping your classroom: If you are interested in flipping your classroom, there are a few things you can do to get started:

- **Start small.** You don't have to flip your entire classroom overnight. Start with a few lessons or units, and then gradually expand your use of the flipped classroom approach.
- **Get feedback from your students.** Ask your students what they like and dislike about the flipped classroom approach. Use their feedback to improve your teaching.
- **Be patient.** It takes time for students and teachers to adjust to a new teaching approach. Don't get discouraged if you don't see results immediately.

How to flip your classroom?

1. Identify the key concepts that your students need to learn.
2. Create resources that students can use to learn about the key concepts outside of class. This could include video lectures, readings, or online activities.
3. Design in-class activities that allow students to apply what they have learned outside of class. This could include problem-solving activities, group work, or projects.
4. Provide students with opportunities to get help from you and from each other. This could include office hours, online discussion forums, or peer tutoring.

Example of a flipped classroom in action:

A math teacher could assign students to watch a video lecture on solving quadratic equations at home. Then, in class, students could work together on a problem set that involves solving quadratic equations. The teacher could circulate around the room and provide help to students as needed.

Flipped classrooms can be used in any subject area, and they can be adapted to meet the needs of all students. If you are interested in flipping your classroom, there are many resources available to help you get started.

Traditional Classroom

The traditional classroom is a physical location where a teacher presents knowledge to students in person. It is the most common type of classroom setting in the world. Traditional classrooms are typically arranged with desks in rows facing the teacher's desk at the front of the room. The teacher delivers instruction to the entire class at once, and students are expected to follow along and complete assignments. Traditional classroom instruction is often based on a standardized curriculum, and tests are administered regularly to assess student learning.

Key features of a traditional classroom:

- **Teacher-centered instruction:** The teacher is the primary source of information and knowledge in the classroom.
- **Whole-class instruction:** The teacher delivers instruction to the entire class at once.
- **Standardized curriculum:** The curriculum is the same for all students in the class.
- **Regular testing:** Students are tested regularly to assess their learning.

Advantages of the traditional classroom:

The traditional classroom has a number of advantages, including:

1. **Efficiency:** The traditional classroom is a very efficient way to deliver instruction to a large group of students.
2. **Community:** The traditional classroom can provide a sense of community and belonging for students.
3. **Structure:** The traditional classroom can provide students with a structured learning environment.
4. **Equity:** The traditional classroom can provide all students with access to the same curriculum and instruction.

Disadvantages of the traditional classroom

The traditional classroom also has a number of disadvantages, including:

1. **Lack of differentiation:** The traditional classroom does not allow for much differentiation to meet the individual needs of all learners.
2. **Passivity:** Students can become passive learners in the traditional classroom, as they are expected to sit quietly and listen to the teacher lecture.
3. **Boredom:** Students can become bored in the traditional classroom, especially if the instruction is not engaging or relevant to their interests.
4. **Competition:** The traditional classroom can foster a competitive environment among students.

How to improve the traditional classroom

There are a number of things that teachers can do to improve the traditional classroom, including:

- **Use a variety of teaching methods:** Teachers should use a variety of teaching methods, such as lectures, discussions, group work, and hands-on activities, to keep students engaged.
- **Differentiate instruction:** Teachers should differentiate instruction to meet the individual needs of all learners. This can be done by providing students with different levels of challenge, offering different learning activities, and allowing students to choose their own learning goals.
- **Create a positive learning environment:** Teachers should create a positive learning environment where students feel safe and respected. This can be done by building relationships with students, creating a classroom culture that promotes cooperation and collaboration, and providing students with opportunities to give and receive feedback.

Here are some examples of the traditional classroom in action:

1. A teacher lectures to a class of students about the history of the American Revolution.
2. A teacher leads a class discussion on the themes of a novel.
3. A teacher divides a class into small groups to work on a math problem-solving activity.
4. A teacher supervises a class of students as they conduct a science experiment.

These are just a few examples of the many ways that the traditional classroom can be used to deliver instruction to students.

Comparison between the flipped classroom and the traditional classroom:

Here is a comparison of the flipped classroom and the traditional classroom in terms of their key features, advantages, and disadvantages:

Feature	Flipped classroom	Traditional classroom
Instructional content delivery	Outside of class	During class
Student engagement	Active engagement in class	Passive engagement in class
Curriculum	Differentiated	Standardized
Assessment	Formative and summative	Summative

Table: 2

Comparison of Advantages between flipped classroom and traditional classroom

Advantage	Flipped classroom	Traditional classroom
Increased student engagement	Students are more engaged in the learning process when they are actively involved in activities, rather than passively listening to lectures.	Students may become passive learners in the traditional classroom, as they are expected to sit quietly and listen to the teacher lecture.
Improved student learning outcomes	Flipped classrooms have been shown to improve student learning outcomes in a variety of subjects.	Traditional classrooms can be effective in delivering instruction to a large group of students.
Increased flexibility for students	Students can learn at their own pace and on their own time outside of class.	Students are expected to follow the pace of the class and complete assignments on the teacher's schedule.
More personalized instruction	Teachers can provide more personalized instruction to students during class time, since they are not spending time lecturing.	Teachers may have difficulty providing personalized instruction to students in a traditional classroom setting, especially if they have a large class size.

Table: 3

Comparison of Disadvantages between flipped classroom and traditional classroom

Disadvantage	Flipped classroom	Traditional classroom
Ensuring that students have access to the necessary technology	Not all students have access to a computer and the internet at home. This can be a barrier to using a flipped classroom approach.	Lack of differentiation
Providing support for students who struggle with learning independently	Some students may need extra support when learning independently outside of class.	Passivity
Competition	The traditional classroom can foster a competitive environment among students.	

Conclusion:**Which approach is better?**

There is no one-size-fits-all answer to the question of which approach is better. The best approach for a particular class or teacher will depend on a variety of factors, such as the subject matter, the students' learning needs, and the teacher's preferences.

Flipped classrooms have the potential to improve student engagement and learning outcomes. However, it is important to ensure that all students have access to the necessary technology and support. Traditional classrooms can be effective in delivering instruction to a large group of students.

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